

EDUCATION AND SCHOOLING

Mavlonova

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To commence with, I prefer to introduce myself. My name is Dilbar Mavlonova and I am an English teacher of governmental school №21 in Bukhara City. I have been working in this sphere more than 10 years (12 years). I have worked in five different governmental schools and at one private school.

Learning is a lifelong process. However, education and schooling are temporary. We undoubtedly need education. But I’m not entirely convinced we need schooling — especially in most schools as they currently are.

Currently, it would not be an exaggeration to say that most people survive and succeed in life not because of but in spite of their schooling. Renowned educationists such as Marc Prensky and Sir Ken Robinson have all pointed out how the current school systems are not fit for purpose. The reason for this is because most teachers, principals, educational boards, and governing bodies aren’t clear in their minds about what the purpose of education is and what the difference between Education, Learning, and Schooling is.

The Purpose of Education is – to create compassionate, creative individuals who can contribute to structure a just society and bringing about positive alteration. In redefining education, the concentration should shift from whole knowledge acquisition to the enhancing of critical thinking skills and problem-solving abilities. By providing a hands-on connection to the real world, education can empower students to improve the lives of others and leave a lasting impact on their community and the world. While education is necessary for human being life, the role of school systems have several drawbacks. Many educators and experts argue that schools often prioritize rote learning and standardized testing rather than promoting critical thinking and creativity. The rigid structure of traditional schooling can hinder individual growth and limit the exploration of personal interests. However, schools still play a role in socializing pupils and providing chances for social interaction and skill improving. It is crucial to rethink and expand the traditional schooling system to better align with the purpose of education.

If we are going to talk about educating and knowledge, I am sure that my country is improving its steps year by year and there are no issues. Technology is also growing and all jobs have started to use proper new technologies for their right sphere. But unfortunately, there is a big problem on teaching. I do not argue that there are a few knowledgeable and intelligent instructors or educators almost all of them got their required degree and level. But one more I prefer to mention that very few of our teachers are focused on teaching or educating. A great deal of them is paying attention to be right idol staff of the government and try to show their fake patriotism and give nearly all attention to school disciplines and education and knowledge automatically gets lower stage in this position. School staff can have a significant impact on controlling behavior, but they cannot always be held accountable for students that misbehave. Rules and norms may be consistently established and enforced, but a teacher may encounter a problem student anyway. There are several reasons why this could be the case. The student could just generally be a problem in any given situation. Some students come from home lives that make it difficult for them to find success in school and later in life. They have little to no guidance, limited food, lack anyone to consistently show them love and care, and must fend for themselves at a young age. This is a recipe for many students in this type of situation to act out, which can cause discipline issues at school.

Other reasons students might misbehave include going through a major life incident. Maybe their parents recently divorced, there is a death they are dealing with, or they recently went through a bad breakup. Other students may just have a hard time getting along with others socially or they may have self-esteem issues. A lack of counseling or social work services in a school could contribute to higher incidences of disciplinary issues. In reflect of this more and more students are suffering from rules of schools. Initially in all schools’ teachers tent to shut students while they want to express something even their opinion and teachers call it “disrespect” and from this school years most of these students began to hide their personal opinion even the perfect ones.

Furthermore, most our programs teach to keep silence while elders speak and never criticize them. Sometimes even youngsters are able to see elders lack points and these cases they should to learn to listen to each other due to fulfill each other. When can we get expected results? In my point of view when we learn to listen our students, when we accept our learners with their whole lack points and when we just to respect their personality. I am not just writing these issues from some articles or posts I am writing them from my 12 years own experience. Even I have worked in various places all schools had similar school rules and regulations and all of them are focused on learners’ appearance. Such as uniform, hairstyle, and individuality. When some students are interested on dancing or singing songs, administration calls to parents and blames students that they are going in wrong way. So, some students are not keen on English or math so where is the problem? So why students have to do their favorite activities in hidden way? Because they are afraid of being criticized and blamed. We should teach and give education to happy and satisfied students and for this case they ought to feel themselves free and loved at school but not afraid and stressed as our teaching society is doing as well.

The following is a list of effective strategies for teachers for promoting positive discipline:

- Teachers must be fair and impartial in enforcing rules and protecting the legal rights of all students.
- They must focus on motivating learners to improve their self-confidence and belief in their abilities to do well.
- Teachers and parents should consider several factors when disciplining learners. Considering whether the disciplinary actions help the child feel a sense of connection, whether it is kind and firm at the same time, and whether it teaches important social and life skills.
- Acknowledge positive behavior when it is not expected
- Be consistent in enforcing rules.
- Avoid handing out lots of warnings without following through on consequences.
- Be fair and impartial in enforcing rules for all students.
- High enrollment figures in educational institutions can result in disciplinary problems.

Although we may not have permission to use it in public schools. However, we can introduce our students to new trends in teaching and learning. It’s true, we can’t change government policies as teachers. We do not have the power to change the parents’ opinion or their financial situation. However, we can make the most of our time. We have the ability to engage, motivate and inspire our students. It is a universal truth that the education system is only as good as its teachers. Let’s demonstrate that we are competent, dedicated and that we are role models for our students.

We all tend to speak about our achievements in our seminars all the time as I notice nearly in all teacher trainings and meetings but there might be a little disagreement with this action as in my perspectives it would be better if we would focus on more our lacks and weak points in our educational system. As a first step I recommend to receive all critics even sometimes we cannot agree with them because critical thinking always gives its result withal positive effect.

REFERENCES

1. “The difference between schooling, learning, and education” Rohan Roberts.
2. “Education vs Schooling (Explained)” December 6, 2023 Tag Vault
3. “School Education” Afzal Badshah, PhD
4. “How to Approach Discipline in School «October 15, 2019 Jon Julius